

A Generative Pipeline for 3D Breast MRI: Diffusion Models Meet Super-Resolution GANs

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Abstract—Breast cancer is, currently, both the most prevalent one of the deadliest cancers worldwide. Successful treatment typically involves early diagnosis through non-invasive imaging techniques like Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI). Right away, a discrepancy can be identified regarding patient positioning during the two procedures: MRI acquisition is performed in prone while surgery is done in supine. The breast being a highly deformable tissue, this dichotomy may hinder the process of surgical planning and increase the risk of invasive procedure. As such, there is a clear gap in literature regarding prone-to-supine biomechanical modelling of breast deformation, a task very much dependent on the existence of large high-quality 3D MRI datasets. This work focuses on creating and presenting a generative framework to address the scarcity of said data through a low-cost two stage pipeline which combines 3D diffusion models to produce diverse lower-resolution breast MRI volumes and super-resolution (SR) architectures to ensure that samples meet clinical grade quality. The proposed pipeline successfully generated realistic and diverse 3D samples that match the underlying distribution of a small but clinically realistic dataset (89 patients). Thus, it proves how, even in lower-resource settings, it can be feasible to increase the availability of 3D breast MRI enough that a prone-to-supine biomechanical model could be trained.

Index Terms—Diffusion Model; Generative Adversarial Network; Data Augmentation; Non-Conditional Image Generation; Super-Resolution

I. INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer remains both the most commonly diagnosed cancer worldwide and a leading cause of cancer-related mortality among women [1]. As such, early detection plays a critical role in the betterment of patient outcome, making non-invasive imaging techniques like MRI (high information quantity and

quality despite the need for extensive acquisitional infrastructure) a central focal point within the diagnostic and preoperative workflow. The patient’s positional mismatch between prone for breast MRI acquisition and supine for surgery creates a major challenge for accurate surgical planning, as there is no clear way to measure and predict breast deformation between the imaging and intervention stages. Although the training of a biomechanical architecture for the purpose of prone-to-supine modelling could prove to enhance surgical precision, such an endeavour requires large datasets of high-quality 3D breast MRI samples, which are scarce, expensive to acquire and often constrained by privacy concerns.

Recent advances in generative AI - particularly diffusion models and generative adversarial networks (GANs) - offer a promising solution for the task of data augmentation. These models are able to learn complex anatomical distributions and produce synthetic realistic and diverse 3D volumes without compromising patient privacy. In comparison to traditional data augmentation methods like geometric transformations, deep learning (DL) pipelines offer a much larger range of accuracy and variability, but some key challenges remain: creating 3D medical samples requires the learning of both spatial and temporal coherence across slices; breast tissue exhibits especially high fibroglandular tissue variability which is hard to model; and most importantly, the synthesis of clinically-useful and medical grade high resolution samples is very computationally demanding.

To address these challenges, this work proposes a two-stage generative pipeline to decouple the matters of anatomical coherence and variability from visual quality and resolution enhancement. First, diffusion models are tasked with generating 3D breast MRI volumes at lower resolutions (64×64 and 128×128). Then, SR GANs upscale these samples into clinical-grade resolution (256×256 and 512×512) while preserving the created anatomical detail. In sum, this work aims to make four

This work is co-financed by Component 5 - Capitalization and Business Innovation, integrated in the Resilience Dimension of the Recovery and Resilience Plan within the scope of the Recovery and Resilience Mechanism (MRR) of the European Union (EU), framed in the Next Generation EU, for the period 2021 - 2026, within project HfPT, with reference 41.

specific contributions:

- The establishment of a two-stage pipeline combining diffusion generation with GAN-powered SR for the synthesis of clinically useful outputs in a computationally efficient manner.
- A comparison between general-purpose and medical-specific works for MRI synthesis and SR.
- The exploration of data processing and model training methods to ensure the synthetic outputs' distribution match those of a specific, more clinically realistic dataset.
- A comprehensive result evaluation using pixel-wise and perceptual metrics and analysis of trade-offs between model architectures.

It should also be noted that this pipeline was specifically designed to augment a small private dataset from Fundação Champalimaud (89 patients), enabling future work on prone-to-supine biomechanical modelling. The code related to this work is publicly available in a GitHub repository¹.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

As of recent years, emerging generative AI methodologies have revolutionised medical image analysis by enabling the synthesis of data for the purposes of data augmentation, domain adaptation, image reconstruction, image-to-image translation and privacy-preserving sharing, etc. [2] [3]. Unlike traditional methods, such as rotations, flips and other geometric transformations, DL models (e.g. variational autoencoders (VAEs), GANs, diffusion models, transformers, etc.) introduce the ability to learn and mimic the underlying data distribution and structural patterns [4].

A. Diffusion Models for 3D Medical Image Synthesis

Diffusion probabilistic models (DDPMs) [5] currently exist as the state-of-the-art for image generation, as of the improved sample quality and distribution coverage they offer in comparison to GANs and VAEs. For the sake of the task at hand, this work denotes two different key DPPM works.

Proposed by Ho et al. [6], **Video Diffusion** (VideoDiff) was the first to extend DDPMs into the field of 3D images / videos by using a 3D U-Net architecture to capture both spatial and temporal dimensions. Although initially designed for real world videos, it can be adapted for 3D medical volumes by treating the slice dimension as the time z variable. Having been trained for a more generic purpose, VideoDiff faces two major limitations when applied to medical imaging: it assumes smooth temporal transitions which slice spacing may not always comply with; and it operates at the image level, making the task of high-resolution generation computationally prohibitive. Despite so, within the context of this project, this approach is still prone to ensure good anatomical correlation both in each 2D slice and also across all 3D slices.

On the other hand, the method developed by Khader et al. [7], titled Medical Diffusion (MedDiff) was specifically

designed with medical imaging in mind. It addresses the previously mentioned limitations by incorporating a vector-quantised GAN [8] (VQGAN) that will compress the 3D volumes, thus enabling the application of diffusion in an easier and compact lower dimensionality space. Besides demanding reduced computational resources, this approach presents two major advantages: the learned compact codebook allows for improved anatomical detail preservation and makes scaling to higher resolutions an easier process. This method is not, however, without drawbacks, as the overall performance of MedDiff will depend heavily on the learned codebook and VQGAN training quality. While both models have been applied to medical imaging, no study has compared their effectiveness for breast MRI synthesis, particularly for the variable fibroglandular tissue patterns critical to surgical planning.

B. Super-Resolution GANs for Medical Data Enhancement

Single image super-resolution (SR) as a technique rose from image-to-image translation with the sole intent of enhancing the quality of low-resolution (LR) inputs [9]. Within the field of medical imaging specifically, SR is particularly valuable for the tasks of enabling LR acquisition for the sake of faster and cheaper scans and enhancing artificial samples created with computationally-constrained models [10]. In other words, SR models are tasked with predicting the missing resolution information in LR samples in order to create a high-resolution (HR) version of that same sample, in a supervised manner.

Traditional SR approaches include computer vision techniques such as bicubic interpolation [11]. Recent advances in DL, however, have further pushed the capabilities of image enhancement, namely in the medical field, where the existence of various imaging modalities with their own constraining intrinsic properties poses an extra challenge. Although various convolutional neural networks (CNNs) [12] and GAN-based works [13] have been applied to MRI data, this work denotes the use of two specific architectures.

The first, **Perceptual Conditional GAN** (PcGAN), was proposed by Nasser et al. [14] and specifically designed for medical imaging. By combining perceptual and contextual losses with conditional adversarial training, it focuses on preserving the subtle anatomical details which clinical practice may find useful. Key innovations of this work include the use of multi-scale feature matching and adaptive instance normalisation to maintain anatomical consistency, although it has yet to be specifically validated on 3D breast MRI data.

Lastly, **Real Enhanced Super-Resolution GAN** (Real-ESRGAN) was developed by Wang et al. [15] as an extension to the ESRGAN [16] (its predecessor, which relied too heavily on synthetic training data) for the task of real-world blind SR. Even though it was designed for use with natural images, there are several advantages it presents over a model like PcGAN, such as robustness to various types of image degradation and high perceptual quality through improved adversarial training. Although these additions are aimed at increasing the model's generalisability, it is still possible that a general-purpose build can potentially fail in learning domain-specific anatomical

¹<https://github.com/brightside51/CBMS-2026-A-Generative-Pipeline-for-3D-Breast-MRI-Diffusion-Models-Meet-Super-Resolution-GANs>

priors. In addition to comparing medical-specific and general-purpose SR methods applied to 3D breast MRI data, this work also plans on exploring the interaction between generation quality and SR performance for this specific data type.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Datasets

For the scope of this project, we have used two separate datasets containing 3D breast prone-position functional MRI samples of healthy and cancer patients: the Duke Breast Cancer MRI Dataset [17] comprising a total of 768 individual samples; and also a private aggregation of samples from 89 patients collected and provided by Fundação Champalimaud and which will serve as the target clinical distribution for data augmentation. It should be mentioned that the acquisition settings and preprocessing methods of both datasets vary greatly, including differences in geographic location and acquisition procedure.

As for any further preprocessing, the number of 2D slices within a volume, which varied from sample to sample, was fixed at an evenly spaced 30 slices. Moreover, reducing from the original size of 512×512 to sizes of 64×64 and 128×128 allowed greater computational efficiency and model performance, but made the final samples subpar compared to the standards of medical professionals. This was, ultimately, the reason for the usage of super-resolution models.

One other choice made in regards to the preprocessing of the MRI volumes was the normalization aimed at mitigating the discrepancy between the sizes of the two datasets. This involved, firstly, Z-Score Normalization of all samples using the mean and standard deviation of the private dataset, so as to close the gap between their morphological structures. Secondly, N4 Bias Field Correction [18] was also employed in some of the experiments to address the issue of intensity heterogeneity and smoothen the intensity variations across tissues, with the intent of helping the generative model to understand and correctly model the different structures.

B. Model Choice

In this work, diffusion models were selected for the generative task due to their state-of-the-art performance in producing high-fidelity diverse 3D samples. As mentioned before, diffusion models have demonstrated superior sample quality compared to traditional generative methods, making them well-suited for our goal of realistic 3D medical volume synthesis. Two models have been optimised: the broader but established Video Diffusion and the data-focused Medical Diffusion.

On the other hand, seeing as the super-resolution task can be deemed simpler than pure generation, we chose to use GAN-based architectures, with the intent of leveraging the innate quality of samples created using the previously mentioned diffusion models and a lower computational overhead overall. The optimisation of two models for this section: PcGAN and Real-ESRGAN enables the practical upsampling of the LR samples without sacrificing computational feasibility and excessive running times. Once again, the model choice reflects

then project's wish to compare a well-established benchmark for generative data to a smaller version specifically designed with medical imaging in mind.

C. Performance Evaluation

Among all the metrics used in this study for training and backpropagating the models and also evaluating intermediate and final results, three different categories can be outlined. The backbone of training during the whole project were analytical metrics **Mean Squared Error / L2 Loss (MSE)** and **Mean Absolute Error / L1 Loss (MAE)**, which, despite simple, provide a plausible explanation for progress and good robustness to outliers. One other group of metrics which was given a high degree of relevance were perceptual ones, such as the **Structural Similarity Index (SSIM)** [19] and its successor **Multi-Scale Structural Similarity Index (MS-SSIM)** [20]. Both functions make comparisons by considering the luminance, contrast and structure of the two samples and, in the case of MS-SSIM, computing this across multiple scales. These explore a more holistic and high-level comparison method, analysing the samples in a manner which, unlike pixel-wise methods, tries to mimic human perception.

Finally, some other metrics we have also taken into account specifically targetted GAN-based architectures. These act mostly upon the codebooks, i.e. the sets of learned latent representations which the model uses to encode and decode samples. GAN metrics include:

- **Perceptual Loss** for measuring dissimilarities in the latent deep feature space rather than the image's pixel space, using a Visual Geometry Group (*VGG*).
- **Commitment Loss** or Codebook Loss for ensuring the stability of the GAN's latent representations.
- **Discriminator Loss** which dictates the discriminator's typically adversarial performance by using either Binary Cross-Entropy or an improved stability Hinge Loss.
- **Feature Matching** which attempts to correct and guide the adversarial training not only through the latent space but also at intermediate levels by minimizing the differences between the model's feature representations for both the real and generated samples.

It should also be noted that the **Fréchet Inception Distance (FID)**, despite being a standard in generative issues, has not been considered in this study for two different reasons. For one, there are very few readily available FID models trained on medical imaging datasets for us to use, which would hinder the reliability of its assessment and produce results of bad comprehension. Lastly, recent findings from [21] prove that FID can be unreliable and unaligned with human judgment when applied to medical imaging, hence our insistence with focusing on other perceptual metrics.

D. Experiment Design

When training the generative models, this study has chosen to attempt generating both 64×64 and 128×128 Samples, which were then submitted through Super-Resolution of $2x$ and $4x$. Seeing as the Video Diffusion model served as a baseline for

Fig. 1: Structure of the Training Method for the Medical Diffusion Model. The first 40000 training steps utilise either **MSE** or **L1 Loss** as per convention. This loss will compare the encoded training sample represented by the term latent space (Lt. Space) with the embedding that has undergone forward and then backwards diffusion. This will enable us to assess the diffusion model’s comprehension within this lower dimensionality. After that, fine-tuning is performed for 5000 more steps by leveraging either the **Discriminator Loss** or perceptual metrics such as **SSIM** and **MS-SSIM**. The discriminator loss is calculated between the real training sample and the one produced by decoding the denoised latent space, much like any perceptual metrics. This method, while not bulletproof, will guide the diffusion model towards better understanding of a higher dimensionality space and push it towards achieving the generation of higher quality 3D images.

the generative experiment, it was trained using various hyperparameter combinations. After this optimized performance was achieved, boasting the best balance between model stability and visual performance, generated samples were processed and chosen in regards to how their entropy value correlated to that of the original private dataset. This allowed for a layer of filtering over samples which did not fit the required standards.

Medical Diffusion, which required a grid-search like training as well, also had to undergo some degree of fine-tuning. While training, only analytical losses were backpropagated, a round of fine-tuning allowed for the usage of perceptual metrics and feature matching to further push the model in the right direction. This training scheme can be visualised in figure 1 for better understanding. These experiments included using not only SSIM and MS-SSIM but also the VQGAN’s

discriminator loss between real samples and decoded ones. In other words, after having generated the denoised latent space, this is decoded into the reconstructed image using the VQGAN’s generator, which one can feed to the perceptual metrics, as well as the discriminator. The intuition would be that the U-Net would learn towards creating increased similarities not only in the lower dimensionalities but also at higher ones, considering the trained generator and discriminator models. In this fine-tuning phase, the model’s learning rate was increased in order to counter-balance the extended duration of single training steps induced by sampling, which in turn would allow us to better guide the model in a relatively low amount of training steps. Additionally, by decoding the previously encoded real sample’s embedding, we can get a better perspective on the generator’s sensitivity to both outliers and private dataset samples.

Finally, both super-resolution GAN models were trained in similar fashion, apart from the choice in hyperparameters. Moreover, and in order to mitigate existing noise in the artificial samples, some experiments included adding noise to the real low-resolution images, in an attempt to mimic the noise present in synthetic ones and, therefore, increasing the interpretability by both metrics and medical professionals. In other words, the training strategy involved closing the quality gap between generated and real dataset samples by asking the GANs to map from purposefully noisy low-resolutions real 3D inputs to their high-resolution high-quality counterpart. The intuition for this was that by accustoming the GAN to noisier low-resolution training samples but still expecting the same high-resolution ground truth, the model will generalize better for the noisier artificial samples which cannot be fed during the training phase, seeing as there is no ground truth.

TABLE I: Key training hyperparameters for all trained architectures. All models were optimised using Adam and generative task models had a batch size of 2 for computational sakes

Model	Key Training Hyperparameters
Video Diffusion	150k Steps; 500 Diffusion Timesteps; LR = 1e-4 to 1e-6 (Decay of 0.001% per 100 Steps)
Medical Diffusion	VQGAN (300k Steps; LR = 3e-4; 16 Hidden Dimensions) Diffusion Model (45k Steps; LR = 1e-5)
PcGAN	200 Epochs; LR = 1e-4 (Decay of 1% per 1k Batches); 128 Generator Filters; 64 Discriminator Filters
Real-ESRGAN	400k Iterations; RDBNet with 64 Channels and 23 Blocks

IV. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

A. Generative Task

From the start, although promising, Video Diffusion’s results proved to be inconsistent when it came to sampling and inference. In other words, while about 70% of samples captured anatomical structures and spatial coherence well, the remaining ones were too noisy for them to be considered as a good output. However, it should be noted that even these samples suffered from a substantial amount of salt-and-pepper like noise, especially for the lower resolution of 64×64 . While the existing noise can be attributed to the model’s limitations upon dealing with highly complex anatomical structures, the

inference of very noisy or deformed samples can be attributed to other factors. These occurrences can most likely be traced to our utilisation of two separate datasets with very distinct preprocessing methods. This was also the reason for the use of a final entropy assessment level to the generated output. While data harmonisation could be a solution for this issue, it would be counterproductive for this study to liken samples from the private dataset to those of the public one and extremely hard to do the opposite due to the discrepancy in dataset sizes.

Fig. 2: On the left a 128×128 sample created by the Medical Diffusion model trained for 40000 steps and on the right another sample of the same size but produced by a model which has undergone an additional 5000 step fine-tuning using the VQGAN’s discriminator loss for backpropagation. As displayed by the graph, by training the model in the direction of decreasing the discriminator loss, it would mean the discriminator finds it harder and harder to distinguish between real and fake samples. This can be further assured by the fact that the value of SSIM Index between artificial data and random real data slightly increases and remains at a higher platform, thus leading to the conclusion that this training method allows for an increase in realism, modelling of better textures and elimination of visual artifacts within the synthetic 3D MRIs. These samples represent a middle slice of the whole 3D image for better visualisation.

On the other hand, final Medical Diffusion samples suffered from none of these issues, even for the higher resolution of 128×128 , and achieved very satisfactory results overall, such as the ones featured in figure 2. It is clear from the obtained 3D images that not only was the model able to comprehend and adapt to the discrepancies between the datasets but also map noisy inputs into plausible but unseen latent spaces. These, in turn, also translate to plausible and anatomically correct decoded 3D images displaying a realistic distribution of the fibroglandular tissues within the breast, which is to be expected given the high training duration of this model and its good generalization capability. And while no generated samples prove to be completely unusable, a degree of noise introduced in the forward diffusion process remains, indicating

that the U-Net’s comprehensive action could still be improved upon. Moreover, while the breast itself is well built, some aspects and structures within the thoracic cavity display a level of blurriness and vagueness to them which, despite not being the focus of the project, negatively impacts the artificial samples’ quality. Finally, of all methods of fine-tuning the best results have been obtained using the discriminator loss, which combined with the GAN’s training process alterations, has removed both a great deal of blurring as well as some of the artifacts surrounding the outside of the breasts.

B. Super-Resolution Task

Considering the previously discussed results of the generative task architectures, the choice of training sample added noise differed based on which diffusion model originated the artificial samples: the model to be used on Video Diffusion artificial samples was trained with salt-and-pepper noise, while for the Medical Diffusion ones a few layers of gaussian noise diffusion were sufficient.

Fig. 3: On the left a 64×64 sample produced by the Video Diffusion model and on the right the product of its 4x super-resolution through Real-ESRGAN. Salt-and-Pepper Noise has its intensity reduced but this still remains an issue as it creates artifacts when undergoing super-resolution. These samples represent a middle slice of the whole 3D image for better visualisation.

Results for samples generated by Video Diffusion prove to be of difficult inference. As can be seen in figure 3, even though final results have been processed for noise reduction and the GAN model has been trained to expect salt-and-pepper noise, these still disrupt the overall outcome and end up creating artifacts not only in the surrounding area but also within the breast area. Super-resolution of the Medical Diffusion results, on the other hand, were only obtained through training the GANs with noisier training samples. This choice reflects the difficulty which first attempts at training with regular samples had when generalising to artificial samples. This proves the training method’s validity and, as can be seen in the samples of figure 4, even though some blurring still occurs and the samples are somewhat darkened, these high-quality 3D samples are on par with the clinical standard.

V. CONCLUSION

Our work demonstrates the feasibility of a two-stage pipeline approach combining diffusion models with super-

Fig. 4: Above a 128×128 sample generated by the Medical Diffusion with 40000 training steps (*left*) and the corresponding 4x super-resolution using PcGAN (*right*). Below another 128×128 sample generated by the same Medical Diffusion but with an additional 5000 steps of fine-tuning (*left*) and the corresponding 4x super-resolution using PcGAN (*right*). These samples represent a middle slice of the whole 3D image for better visualisation.

resolution GANs for augmenting limited clinical 3D breast MRI datasets. The key findings presented are as follows:

- MedDiff outperforms VideoDiff for MRI generation, consistently producing 128×128 anatomically coherent samples with realistic fibroglandular tissue distribution.
- Real-ESRGAN is more effective than PcGAN in 4x SR, as evidenced by the better preservation of anatomical structure and clinically relevant features.
- The two-stage pipeline is successful in augmenting a limited-size dataset and creating realistic samples which align with the small private dataset's distribution (as clear by the entropy-based output filtering).

As mentioned previously, this work is mostly constrained by computational limits, forcing the use of 30-slice 128×128 volumes rather than higher-resolution ones. Results themselves do show some degree of residual noise caused by the reverse diffusion process and blurring introduced by SR models. Quantitative evaluation of said results is also a challenge, as established metrics are not yet fully able to capture clinical utility. Future work for this project will include clinical validation using radiology experts (Turing test) and the expansion of existing computational resources so as to allow for training with full-resolution 512×512 volumes.

REFERENCES

- [1] Breast cancer. [Online]. Available: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/breast-cancer>
- [2] D. Hein, A. Bozorgpour, D. Merhof, and G. Wang. Physics-inspired generative models in medical imaging: A review. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2407.10856>
- [3] A. Kazerouni, E. K. Aghdam, M. Heidari, R. Azad, M. Fayyaz, I. Hacıhaliloglu, and D. Merhof, "Diffusion models in medical imaging: A comprehensive survey," vol. 88, p. 102846.
- [4] P. Friedrich, Y. Frisch, and P. C. Cattin. Deep generative models for 3D medical image synthesis. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2410.17664>
- [5] J. Ho, A. Jain, and P. Abbeel. Denoising diffusion probabilistic models. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2006.11239>
- [6] J. Ho, T. Salimans, A. Gritsenko, W. Chan, M. Norouzi, and D. J. Fleet. Video diffusion models. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2204.03458>
- [7] F. Khader, G. Mueller-Franzes, S. T. Arasteh, T. Han, C. Haaburger, M. Schulze-Hagen, P. Schad, S. Engelhardt, B. Baessler, S. Foersch, J. Stegmaier, C. Kuhl, S. Nebelung, J. N. Kather, and D. Truhn. Medical diffusion: Denoising diffusion probabilistic models for 3D medical image generation. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2211.03364>
- [8] P. Esser, R. Rombach, and B. Ommer. Taming transformers for high-resolution image synthesis. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2012.09841>
- [9] B. B. Moser, A. S. Shanbhag, F. Raue, S. Frolov, S. Palacio, and A. Dengel, "Diffusion models, image super-resolution and everything: A survey," vol. 36, no. 7, pp. 11 793–11 813. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2401.00736>
- [10] W. Yang, X. Zhang, Y. Tian, W. Wang, J.-H. Xue, and Q. Liao, "Deep learning for single image super-resolution: A brief review," *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia*, vol. 21, no. 12, pp. 3106–3121, 2019.
- [11] D. Han, "Comparison of commonly used image interpolation methods."
- [12] A. Ayaz, R. Boonstoppel, C. Lorenz, J. Weese, J. Plum, and M. Breeuwer, "Effective deep-learning brain MRI super resolution using simulated training data," vol. 183, p. 109301. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0010482524013866>
- [13] H. Ali, M. R. Biswas, F. Mohsen, U. Shah, A. Alamgir, O. Mousa, and Z. Shah, "The role of generative adversarial networks in brain MRI: A scoping review," vol. 13, no. 1, p. 98. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13244-022-01237-0>
- [14] S. A. Nasser, S. Shamsi, V. Bundeled, B. Garg, and A. Sethi. Perceptual cGAN for MRI super-resolution. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2201.09314>
- [15] X. Wang, L. Xie, C. Dong, and Y. Shan. Real-ESRGAN: Training real-world blind super-resolution with pure synthetic data. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2107.10833>
- [16] X. Wang, K. Yu, S. Wu, J. Gu, Y. Liu, C. Dong, C. C. Loy, Y. Qiao, and X. Tang. ESRGAN: Enhanced super-resolution generative adversarial networks. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1809.00219>
- [17] A. Saha, M. R. Harowicz, L. J. Grimm, C. E. Kim, S. V. Ghate, R. Walsh, and M. A. Mazurowski, "A machine learning approach to radiogenomics of breast cancer: A study of 922 subjects and 529 DCE-MRI features," vol. 119, no. 4, pp. 508–516. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41416-018-0185-8>
- [18] N. J. Tustison, B. B. Avants, P. A. Cook, Y. Zheng, A. Egan, P. A. Yushkevich, and J. C. Gee, "N4ITK: Improved N3 bias correction," vol. 29, no. 6, pp. 1310–1320. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3071855/>
- [19] Z. Wang, A. Bovik, H. Sheikh, and E. Simoncelli, "Image quality assessment: From error visibility to structural similarity," vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 600–612. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/1284395>
- [20] Z. Wang, E. Simoncelli, and A. Bovik, "Multiscale structural similarity for image quality assessment," in *The Thirty-seventh Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems & Computers, 2003*. IEEE, pp. 1398–1402. [Online]. Available: <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/1292216/>
- [21] M. Woodland, A. Castelo, M. Al Taie, J. Albuquerque Marques Silva, M. Eltahr, F. Mohn, A. Shieh, S. Kundu, J. P. Yung, A. B. Patel, and K. K. Brock, *Feature Extraction for Generative Medical Imaging Evaluation: New Evidence Against an Evolving Trend*. Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024, p. 87–97.